

Influence of Information Literacy Skills on Publication Output of Lecturers in Imo State University, Owerri

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Abstract

This study explored how information literacy (IL) skills affect the publication output of lecturers at Imo State University, Owerri. It specifically assessed lecturers' IL abilities, examined their research productivity, analysed the link between IL skills and research outputs, identified challenges, and suggested strategies for improvement. Using a descriptive survey design, the study involved 16 LIS lecturers as the population. Data were gathered via a structured questionnaire and analysed using descriptive statistics, such as mean scores, frequency counts, and percentages. Results show that while lecturers have basic IL skills, there are gaps in advanced areas such as reference management software, plagiarism checkers, and sophisticated search strategies. Publication output is moderate, with more publications in local and national outlets than in international journals. The study recommends that improving IL skills through ongoing training, better infrastructure, and supportive policies could boost lecturers' research productivity and their institution's visibility.

Keywords: Information literacy skills, Publication output, Lecturers

Introduction

Academic publishing remains a vital indicator of scholarly productivity, reputation, and institutional visibility. Universities, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria, assess the effectiveness of their teaching and research staff not only by classroom engagement but also through their contributions to global knowledge via publications in peer-reviewed journals, books, and conference proceedings. However, lecturers' ability to contribute meaningfully to academic publishing is greatly affected by their information literacy skills (Sulehri, Rafiq & Arshad, 2024). Information literacy, broadly defined, is the competence to recognise when information is needed and to locate, evaluate, and use it effectively and ethically. In today's digital age, lecturers must navigate vast amounts of information across databases, e-libraries, open-access repositories, and other scholarly platforms. Yet many encounter challenges, including insufficient digital literacy, limited exposure to advanced search techniques, and poor referencing practices, all of which hinder their productivity.

According to the American Library Association (ALA), "Information literacy is a set of abilities requiring individuals to recognise when information is needed and can locate, evaluate, and use needed information electively" (ALA, 2000). The University of North Texas (2025) states that information literacy skills are increasingly important due to the growing complexity of the modern environment, characterised by rapid

technological change and expanding sources of information. People are confronted with a diverse and plentiful array of information choices — in their academic pursuits, in the workplace, and in their personal lives.

Imo State University, Owerri, as a dynamic academic hub, aims to compete on the global research stage. However, it appears that some lecturers find it challenging to utilise modern information resources effectively for high-quality research. This prompts an important question: how do information literacy skills affect lecturers' publication output at the university? This study explores the connection between information literacy skills and scholarly productivity among the university's lecturers. The goal is to highlight the importance of IL skills and provide recommendations for training, institutional support, and strategies to enhance the university's reputation through increased research publications.

Statement of the Problem

Publication output remains a key requirement for academic promotion, career advancement, and institutional ranking. However, observations suggest that many lecturers in Nigerian universities have relatively low research productivity compared to their peers in more developed countries. This shortfall is often linked to poor information literacy skills, limited access to digital resources, and a lack of training opportunities. While some lecturers demonstrate fundamental skills in searching and citing, others struggle with more advanced practices, such as using reference managers, plagiarism-detection tools, or sophisticated database search techniques. As a result, their publications tend to be concentrated in local journals with limited international visibility. Therefore, it is important to empirically examine how information literacy skills influence lecturers' publication output at Imo State University, Owerri.

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine the influence of information literacy skills on the publication output of lecturers in Imo State University, Owerri. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Assess the level of information literacy skills possessed by lecturers in IMSU
2. Examine lecturers' publication output in terms of quantity and quality.
3. Determine the relationship between information literacy skills and publication output.
4. Identify the challenges lecturers face in utilising IL skills for research productivity.
5. Proffer strategies to enhance lecturers' IL competencies for improved publication output.

Literature Review

Concept of Information Literacy

Information literacy is not just about searching for information but involves a deep understanding of how to evaluate the credibility of sources, synthesise information from various perspectives, and use it ethically. The ability to distinguish reliable from misleading information is especially important in an academic setting, where students must rely on credible sources for research and learning (Julien & Barker, 2022). Information literacy refers to the ability to recognise when information is needed and to locate, evaluate, and use it effectively. In academic libraries, it enables students and faculty members to access a wide range of resources, including books, journals, research databases, and digital repositories. According to Musa and Ibrahim (2021), information literacy is a core skill for academic success, as it enables users to navigate library systems efficiently, critically assess information sources, and apply relevant data in their research

and studies. Information literacy has become a key skill in higher education. The American Library Association (ALA, 2000) describes it as the ability to recognise when information is needed and to locate, assess, and utilise it effectively. In a university setting, information literacy skills include database searching, critical assessment of sources, referencing, avoiding plagiarism, and ethical use of information. It is not just a technical ability but a lifelong learning skill that enables lecturers to produce high-quality research. For example, a lecturer who can navigate databases such as Scopus, Web of Science, or JSTOR is more likely to access the latest literature supporting impactful publications.

Publication Output in Universities

Publication output denotes the measurable scholarly contributions of academics, including journal articles, books, chapters, conference papers, and technical reports. It serves as a key criterion in academic promotion, institutional ranking, and global visibility. Studies such as Okiki (2013) and Nwosu and Igwe (2021) indicate that Nigerian universities face challenges of low research productivity, often due to limited information literacy skills, insufficient research funding, and poor infrastructure.

Relationship between Information Literacy (IL) Skills and Publication Output

The link between information literacy and publication productivity is well-documented. Aina (2023) observed that lecturers with higher IL competencies are more likely to publish in reputable journals. Similarly, Baro and Keboh (2012) found that Nigerian academics often lack advanced search strategies, leading to reliance on low-quality or inaccessible materials. IL training has been shown to significantly increase both the quantity and quality of research outputs (Kumar & Gor, 2019).

Challenges in Applying IL Skills

Despite the importance of IL, lecturers face several obstacles:

- Inadequate access to subscription-based databases.
- Limited training opportunities in IL.
- Poor ICT infrastructure and inconsistent internet connectivity.
- Lack of institutional incentives for publishing.

These challenges reduce the effectiveness of lecturers’ IL competencies, thereby affecting their publication productivity.

Figure 1: The Information Literacy–Publication Productivity Model (IL-PPM) by the researcher

The diagram depicts a conceptual framework illustrating the link between information literacy skills and publication output, with mediating factors that affect this connection. Skills such as searching for information, evaluating sources, proper citation, using reference tools, and avoiding plagiarism act as the independent variables that enhance researchers' capacity to produce scholarly work. These skills contribute to increased publication output, including journal articles, books, book chapters, conference papers, and citations. However, the strength of this relationship is strengthened by mediating factors such as access to e-resources, institutional support, and reliable internet connectivity, which aid in the effective application of information literacy skills in scholarly publishing.

Research Methodology

This study employed a descriptive survey design. The population consisted of 16 individuals, all faculty members in the LIS Department at Imo State University, Owerri. A total census approach was adopted due to the manageable population size. A structured questionnaire served as the data collection instrument. Data were analysed using mean scores, frequency counts, and simple percentages. A five-point Likert rating scale was utilised, with a criterion mean of 3.00 and above indicating agreement, while scores below 3.00 signified disagreement.

One limitation of this study is that it was conducted at a single institution, which may limit the extent to which the findings can be applied to other universities with different research environments and support systems. The study also relied on self-reported responses from lecturers, which may be influenced by personal bias or overestimates of information literacy skills and publication output. Furthermore, the study primarily focused on specific information literacy competencies and might not have considered other factors affecting research productivity, such as disciplinary differences, workload, and funding opportunities. These limitations may affect the extent to which the results can be interpreted.

Results

Table 1: Information literacy skills of lecturers

S/n	Item question	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	Remark
1	I can effectively search for scholarly information in online databases.	5	2	1	8	0	3.3	Agreed
2	I know how to evaluate the credibility and relevance of sources.	10	0	0	3	3	3.9	Agreed
3	I am able to use reference management tools	2	0	1	4	9	1.90	Disagreed

	(e.g., Mendeley, EndNote, Zotero).							
4	I can correctly apply citation styles (APA, MLA, Chicago, etc.).	10	0	6	0	0	4.3	Agreed
5	I understand how to avoid plagiarism through proper paraphrasing and citation.	5	0	5	4	2	3.1	Agreed
6	I frequently use advanced search techniques (Boolean operators, truncation, filters).	2	2	5	7	0	2.90	Disagreed
7	I am confident in accessing and using the university's subscribed e-resources	3	6	3	0	4	3.3	Agreed

This table shows the information literacy skills of lecturers across seven core competencies. Responses were measured on a five-point Likert scale, and mean scores were used to determine the level of proficiency in each skill area. A decision rule was applied where a mean score of 3.00 and above indicates agreement while below 3.00 indicates disagreement with the item statement. From the above table, it can be deduced that use of reference management tools such as Mendeley, EndNote, Zotero; and advanced search skills (applying Boolean operators, truncation, filters) are major skill deficiency among lecturers in LIS, having attracted below the criterion mean of 3.00.

Table 2: Publication output of lecturers

S/N	Item	Response Options	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1	Journal articles published in the last 5 years	None	0	0%
		1-3	3	19%
		4-6	8	50%
		7-9	3	19%
		10+	2	12%
2	Books or book chapters published in 5 years	None	4	25%
		1-2	8	50.0%
		3-4	3	19%

S/N	Item	Response Options	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
3	Frequency of conference presentations	5+	1	6%
		Rarely	2	13%
		Occasionally	9	56%
4	Where most publications appear	Frequently	5	31%
		Local journals	10	62%
		National journals	3	19%
5	My publications have received significant citations	International journals	3	19%
		Strongly Agree	1	6%
		Agree	4	25%
		Neutral	7	44%
		Disagree	3	19%
		Strongly Disagree	1	6%

Table 2 displays lecturers' responses regarding their productivity over the past five years. Most lecturers (50%) published 4-6 journal articles during this period. About 12% produced more than 10 papers, indicating a small group of highly productive researchers. Half of the lecturers (50%) published 1-2 books or book chapters, while 25% had none, suggesting moderate engagement with scholarly book writing, which is common in many Nigerian universities. A majority (56%) present papers at conferences only occasionally, while 31% do so frequently. This indicates that although lecturers produce publications, their conference participation remains relatively low, possibly due to funding or workload constraints. A significant majority (62%) publish mainly in local journals, with only 19% publishing in international peer-reviewed journals. A large proportion (44%) remained neutral about whether their work receives significant citations, implying uncertainty or limited tracking of citation metrics. Only 31% agreed or strongly agreed, reflecting low-to-moderate citation impact overall.

Table 3: Relationship between information literacy skills and publication output

S/n	Item question	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	Remark
1	My ability to access scholarly databases influences my publication productivity.	8	4	2	2	0	4.06	Agreed
2	Lack of IL skills has sometimes limited my ability to publish	5	3	4	5	0	3.50	Agreed

	in reputable journals.							
3	Training in IL skills has directly improved the quality of my research output.	7	5	2	2	0	4.06	Agreed
4	Effective use of IL skills increases my chances of being published in international journals.	6	4	3	3	0	3.81	Agreed

This table presents the responses regarding the relationship between information literacy and publication output of lecturers in the LIS department. Respondents generally agree that access to scholarly databases significantly influences their ability to be productive in research publication. The high number of “Strongly Agree” (8 out of 16), among others, suggests that lecturers who can easily access journals, articles, and e-resources tend to write and publish more frequently.

Table 4: Challenges in utilising information literacy skills

S/n	Item question	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	Remark
1	Poor access to subscription-based journals limits my research productivity.	7	5	2	2	0	4.06	Agreed
2	I lack adequate training opportunities in information literacy.	6	4	3	3	0	3.81	Agreed
3	Poor internet connectivity affects my ability to use e-resources.	5	6	3	2	0	3.88	Agreed
4	I face difficulties in using plagiarism checkers or referencing software.	4	5	4	3	0	3.56	Agreed
5	Limited institutional support discourages active publishing	6	3	3	3	1	3.69	Agreed

The above table reveals that most lecturers strongly agree that limited access to subscription-based journals restricts their research productivity. This indicates that even if lecturers have the skills, the

availability of scholarly resources is a critical limiting factor. Additionally, inadequate training opportunities and insufficient institutional support, among other issues, hinder effective use of IL skills. This suggests a need for structured workshops on database searching, referencing tools, and plagiarism management. Institutional support, such as research grants, conference allowances, or recognition, should be encouraged to promote research engagement.

Table 5: Strategies to enhance information literacy skills

S/n	Item question	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	Remark
1	Regular IL training workshops should be organised for lecturers.	10	5	1	0	0	4.20	Agreed
2	The university should provide better access to e-resources and databases.	9	6	1	0	0	3.95	Agreed
3	Internet facilities should be upgraded for seamless research access.	8	6	2	0	0	4.00	Agreed
4	Incentives (grants, awards, promotions) should be tied to quality publications.	7	6	2	1	0	3.85	Agreed
5	Collaboration with librarians should be encouraged for IL skill enhancement.	6	7	2	1	0	4.00	Agreed

This table presents lecturers' responses to strategies to improve information literacy skills. Lecturers overwhelmingly support organising regular IL workshops, providing access to e-resources, and other measures as effective strategies for enhancing IL skills. This suggests that ongoing professional development is crucial for improving database searching and referencing skills and preventing plagiarism.

Discussion of Findings

The overall pattern of mean scores indicates that lecturers at the institution generally possess moderate to high information literacy skills, with particular strengths in citation skills, evaluating the credibility of sources, and using e-resources (moderate to high). However, notable weaknesses were identified in using reference management tools and advanced search techniques. These skill gaps may impact research quality

and efficiency in academic writing. Regarding publication output over the last five years, the findings show that, although lecturers demonstrate a moderate publication output—mainly in journal articles and book chapters—their publications are mostly confined to local journals, and they attend conferences only occasionally. Citation impact remains modest, and only a small percentage engage in higher-level scholarly dissemination, such as publishing in international journals. This pattern suggests a need for increased research funding, enhanced capacity for international publication, mentorship programmes, collaborations to boost global visibility, and encouragement to monitor citation metrics using tools like Google Scholar, Scopus, and ResearchGate.

Regarding the relationship between IL and publication output, the mean score ranges from 3.50 to 4.06 across the four items. This indicates that: Information literacy skills significantly contribute to research productivity, access to databases is the most important factor enhancing productivity, IL training is seen as beneficial for improving the quality and credibility of research work. Many lecturers believe that effective IL skills can help achieve international visibility, although other structural factors still present challenges; a moderate number still face gaps in IL, which may partly explain why most publications are limited to local journals. These results suggest that strengthening IL skills through ongoing training, better access to electronic resources, and enhanced research support systems could substantially increase lecturers' publication output, particularly in reputable and international outlets.

Regarding the challenges lecturers face in utilising information literacy skills for research productivity, findings reveal that structural and infrastructural factors, rather than purely skill deficits, are the main barriers to effective use of IL skills. Key challenges include access to subscription-based journals, internet connectivity, lack of dedicated IL training, and limited institutional support. The study findings show a strong consensus among lecturers on strategies to improve IL skills. The main strategies are regular IL training workshops, better access to e-resources and databases, upgraded internet facilities, incentives, and collaboration with librarians.

Conclusion

Information literacy is more than just a technical skill; it is the lifeblood of academic publishing. For lecturers at Imo State University, Owerri, mastering IL competencies directly influences their ability to publish and enhance the institution's global reputation. By empirically analysing the relationship between IL skills and publication output, this study highlights the importance of ongoing IL training, better access to resources, and stronger institutional support to promote research excellence.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Regular information literacy training workshops should be organised for lecturers, with emphasis on advanced search techniques and the effective use of reference management tools.
2. Improved access to subscription-based databases and e-resources should be provided to enhance lecturers' ability to access high-quality scholarly materials.

3. Reliable and high-speed internet connectivity should be upgraded to support efficient research and access to online academic resources.
4. Institutional support systems, including research funding and administrative support, should be strengthened to promote higher research productivity.
5. Mentorship programmes and research collaborations should be encouraged to help lecturers publish in reputable and international journals.
6. Lecturers should be encouraged to track their research impact using citation platforms such as Google Scholar and other academic profiling tools.

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